

**IMPACT OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON SECONDARY EDUCATION IN RIVERS
STATE, NIGERIA**

Charles Meelubari Itaa

Center for Occupational Health, Safety and Environment,
Institute of Petroleum Studies, University of Port Harcourt
Choba, Rivers State Nigeria

Patience Itaa, Ph.D

School of Community Health
Rivers State College of Health Science and Management Technology
Port Harcourt

Ngozi Dennis Willy

School of Community Health
Rivers State College of Health Science and Management Technology
Port Harcourt

Abstract

At a period when Nigerian schools were temporarily closed due to the COVID-19 outbreak, this paper explored and focused on the nature of the education system and its many shortcomings. The COVID-19 epidemic had a significant influence on Nigeria's educational system, notably in Rivers State. With the exception of a few private institutions, which immediately transitioned to virtual learning platforms, all instructional activities were ceased. It also highlighted differences between Nigerian students and international students. The epidemic gave the country a chance to assess the status of its educational system. Prior to the outbreak, the Nigerian education system in primary, secondary, and most universities relied solely on traditional chalkboard instruction and learning. Electronic devices were not provided in public schools to enhance teaching and learning, nor were students allowed to possess or bring their own devices to school, particularly in elementary and secondary schools. Teachers and students were at a loss as to how to continue teaching and learning in the face of the COVID-19 outbreak, which resulted in a lockdown situation and school closure. The major objective of this paper was to examine COVID-19's issues and impacts on education in Nigeria, with focus on Rivers State.